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Global scale modelling within EMEP:
Progress report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Atmospheric dispersion of a number of pollutants under the scope of the LRTAP Convention is not limited by a regional scale. As a result pollution levels in the EMEP region can be significantly affected by emissions from distant sources situated in other regions or even continents. It is largely related to such long-lived substances as mercury and POPs as well as to ozone and particular matter. Taking into account importance of the impact of external continental sources, and of intercontinental transport of the pollutants, the two EMEP modelling Centres (MSC-W and MSC-E) have extended their modelling abilities to a global scale. Efforts of the Centres in this field include elaboration of chemical transport models capable of global scale simulations, preparation of required input information (emissions, meteorological fields, geophysical data, etc.) as well as evaluation of the models against observations and multi-model intercomparisons.

The two global scale models developed at MSC-W and MSC-E (EMEP/MSC-W and GLEMOS, respectively) participated in the multi-model experiments performed as a part of the EMEP Task Force on Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (TF HTAP) Assessment [HTAP, 2010]. The main focus of the TF HTAP is the determination of the extent and impact of the intercontinental transport of air pollution and to foster international co-operation in this field. The Centres have made valuable contributions to the TF HTAP Assessment 2010 taking part in both model simulations and analysis of the multi-model experiments.

This report contains an overview of the EMEP modelling Centres research activities associated with global scale modelling and model developments. This year the work of the Centres was focused on improvement of the model parameterisations of physical and chemical processes, the model applications and evaluation against measurements.

MSC-W continued work on elaboration of the global mode of the EMEP/MSC-W model. The model has undergone a large number of changes over the last few years, many of these designed to make the model more flexible for different scales, including global. In particular, the emission processing for biogenic VOC emissions were completely re-written; the SOA and EC modelling were further integrated into the core EMEP model system; a preliminary soil-NO_x emission routine for global applications was added. Besides, some small changes to the chemical scheme and hundreds of technical code changes to improve structure or ease of use, and for different applications (e.g. forecasting, global modelling, nested model runs) were implemented into the model.

Both the regional and global-scale mode of the EMEP/MSC-W model were compared with Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements of CO at six European stations. The agreement between the FTIR measurements and the model calculations were better for the global calculations compared to the regional model calculations, in particular at high latitudes. The global model was also used to explain the negative trends seen in the measured FTIR CO columns. Moreover, a number of model sensitivity runs were performed to study the effects of the cloud acidity and wet deposition rates on simulation results and to improve the model performance that was also discussed in connection with implementation of the model results in the AEROCOM tool.

Global source receptor calculations of the contributions from EMEP countries to global aerosol loading and aerosol radiative forcing were extended by MSC-W to include the effects of sources outside Europe, as the USA, Canada, China etc. and world-wide shipping. The results from the model calculations have been included in the GAINS model. This required extension of the model to represent emissions of all necessary species and introducing respective metrics. While the optimization

considering all additional constraints is still under development, IIASA has developed new BC, OC and CO emission data for the whole EMEP domain, implemented the normalized radiative forcings, and performed first calculations for the baseline scenario and a control case where only options reducing radiative forcings have been selected.

MSC-E continues development of the Global EMEP Multi-media Modelling System (GLEMOS). This new modelling framework is aimed to provide effective means for multi-scale simulations of the environment pollution with various contaminants. Application of the framework on a global scale allows assessing intercontinental transport of long-lived pollutants and its contribution to pollution levels in the EMEP region. The key feature of the modelling system is the modular architecture providing a flexible approach to multi-pollutant and multi-media simulations. The latter are principal for study of long-term cycling and accumulation of such substances as mercury and POPs. This year the development has been mainly focused on improvement of the global framework architecture, further elaboration of the multi-media approach and refining of the mercury chemical scheme.

Significant efforts were undertaken to improve and further develop meteorological and oceanic pre-processors required for input data support of the model simulations. A new version of the WRF model was adapted for use as a meteorological driver for GLEMOS. An advantage of WRF is possibility of data support of multi-scale simulations (from global to local) on different projections and grids. MSC-E also started development of the oceanological driver to supply the multi-media simulations with required data on sea currents, temperature, salinity, etc. based on the Parallel Ocean Program (POP) model. In addition, the oceanic transport module describing pollutant's dispersion in the ocean was re-designed and thoroughly tested.

Another important activity of GLEMOS development was improvement of mercury chemical scheme in line with the new findings of the research community. In particular, the chemical mechanism of mercury oxidation by reactive halogens was considerably refined in its application to fast chemical kinetics in the Arctic. The updated version of the framework was also applied for simulation of mercury transport on a global scale and it was thoroughly evaluated against measurements. For this purpose, a database of global wide measurements mercury species in air and wet deposition fluxes was collected from both available monitoring networks and literature survey. Evaluation of modelling results against measurements was demonstrated satisfactory performance of GLEMOS in mercury simulations.

The EMEP modelling Centres (MSC-E and MSC-W) will continue their work on further development and application of their modeling tools on a global scale. MSC-W will refine the washout parameterization of the Unified EMEP model, improve the biogenic emission modules (NO_x, BVOC), evaluate of the model against non-European sites as well as elaborate and test the nesting procedure from global to regional scale computations. MSC-E will further develop and improve of the modular architecture of the GLEMOS modelling framework (including the nesting capabilities and computational efficiency), incorporate data on aerosols and atmospheric reactants for heavy metal and POPs simulations, and perform a comprehensive analysis of major physical and chemical processes governing mercury cycling in the atmosphere. The Centres will also continue co-operation with the EMEP Task Force on Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (TF HTAP).

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INTRODUCTION

Assessment of the environment pollution by a variety of contaminants (acidifying and eutrophying compounds, ozone, particulate matter, heavy metals, and POPs) is the primary task of the Cooperative Programme for Monitoring and Evaluation of Long-range Transmission of Air Pollutants in Europe (EMEP). The geographical scope of the EMEP tasks was commonly restricted by territories of the EMEP countries including the European region and adjacent areas. However, for a number of reasons there is a tendency to extend the scope of the assessment to larger scales.

First of all, it is motivated by the evidence that atmospheric dispersion of some of the pollutants is not limited by a regional scale. Therefore, the pollution levels in the EMEP domain can be significantly affected by emissions from distant sources situated in other regions or even continents. It is largely related to such long-lived substances as mercury and POPs as well as to ozone and particular matter. The potential to long-range transport of mercury and POPs is enhanced by their ability to be re-emitted after deposition to the ground that leads to multi-hop dispersion over long-distances. Besides, even deposition of pollutants with relatively short residence time in the atmosphere (e.g. sulphur and nitrogen compounds, lead and cadmium) is influenced by sources located outside the region of interest, particularly, in the Asian countries with growing economies. Therefore, correct consideration of these sources is required through evaluation appropriate boundary conditions.

Moreover, a number of tasks related to climate change and its effect on air pollution also require consideration on wider spatial scales. Some of the pollutants considered under the LRTAP Convention (hereafter the Convention) have short-term radiative forcing effect on climate. These include black carbon, sulphur and ozone precursors. Obviously there may be co-benefits as measures taken to reduce emissions under the Convention may also reduce emissions of the pollutants covered by the Kyoto protocol and vice versa.

Recognizing the above mentioned importance of the impact of external continental sources, and of intercontinental transport of the pollutants, the two EMEP modelling centres (MSC-W and MSC-E) have extended their modelling abilities to a global scale. Efforts of the centres in this field include elaboration of chemical transport models capable of global scale simulations, preparation of required input information (emissions, meteorological fields, geophysical data, etc.) as well as evaluation of the models against observations and in multi-model intercomparisons. In addition, MSC-E suggested the concept of a common modelling framework in order to co-ordinate the model developments on a global scale. It consists of elaboration of a common library of program modules, collection of a database of input parameters, and harmonisation of the module interfaces and the data formats [Jonson and Travníkov, 2010]. Progress of the Centres in the field of the global scale model developments was described in a series of joint technical reports [Tarrasón and Gusev, 2008; Travníkov et al., 2009; Jonson and Travníkov, 2010].

The two global scale models developed at MSC-W and MSC-E (Unified EMEP and GLEMOS, respectively) participated in the multi-model experiments performed as a part of the EMEP Task Force on Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (TF HTAP) Assessment [HTAP, 2010]. The main focus of the TF HTAP is the determination of the extent and impact of the intercontinental transport of air pollution and to foster international co-operation in this field. The Centres have made valuable contribution to the TF HTAP Assessment 2010 in both model simulations and analysis of the multi-model experiments. The work of TF HTAP will continue to develop a fuller scientific understanding of the

intercontinental transport of air pollution across the Northern Hemisphere; its impacts on health, ecosystems, and climate; and the linkages between regional air pollution and climate change. The Centres will participate in a new round of the multi-model experiments including assessment of regional boundary conditions, source attribution, and source-receptor sensitivities under future abatement scenarios (*ECE/EB.AIR/GE.1/2011/10*).

This report contains an overview of the EMEP modelling Centres research activities associated with global scale modelling and model developments. This year the work of the Centres was focused on improvement of the model parameterisations of physical and chemical processes, the model application and evaluation against measurements. In particular, Chapter 1 contains evaluation of the Unified EMEP model vs. observations of CO, source-receptor calculations of short lived climate forcers and incorporation of near-term radiative forcing in the GAINS model, sensitivity tests as well as inclusion of the model results in the AEROCOM tool. New developments of GLEMOS are given in Chapter 2 including improvement of the framework modular architecture, adaptation and testing a new meteorological pre-processor based on the WRF model, development of the oceanological driver for multi-media simulations along with the oceanic transport module, application of the framework for mercury simulations and evaluation of the modelling results. Future activities of the centres in the field of the global scale modelling are formulated in Chapter 3.

1. GLOBAL MODEL CALCULATIONS WITH THE UNIFIED EMEP MODEL

Referring to the global version of the Unified EMEP photochemistry model, the underlying material presented in this report has been prepared in various stages over the past year. Part of the material is based on ongoing work for the Norwegian ministry of the Environment on the physical and economic aspects of climate change and air pollution interactions.

As noted in *Simpson et al.* [2010], the EMEP MSC-W model has undergone a large number of changes over the last few years, many of these designed to make the model more flexible for different scales, including global. During 2010-2011, the following changes can be mentioned:

1. The emission processing for biogenic VOC emissions has been completely re-written, making use of updated emission rates and maps of forest species from *Köble and Seufert* [2001] over Europe. This work [also used by *Karl et al.* 2009 and *Kesik et al.* 2005] provided maps for 115 tree species in 30 European countries, based upon a compilation of data from the ICP-forest network [UN-ECE, 1998]. This European map is merged in the code with revised default BVOC emission rates for different landcover categories which are applied at the global scale.
2. The SOA model and EC modelling were further integrated into the core EMEP model system, and can be run globally.
3. A preliminary soil-NO_x emission routine for global applications was added.
4. Some small changes to the chemical scheme, e.g. the rate of coarse nitrate formation from N₂O₅ has been reduced to loosely reflect the findings of *Riemer et al.* [2009].
5. 100s of technical code changes to improve structure or ease of use, and for different applications (e.g. forecasting, global modelling, nested model runs). Systems to generate some missing meteorological parameters (e.g. 3-D precip) from readily available data (for this example, surface precipitation) were implemented, allowing the use of archived data from GCM runs for example.

Documentation of the latest version of the model is being written up for submission to the Atmos. Chemistry and Physics special issue on 'EMEP an integrated system of models and observations in support of European air quality and policy'.

1.1. Comparing model results with FTIR measurements of CO

Jon Angelbratt, Jan Eiof Jonson and David Simpson

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is a tool for measuring a wide range of atmospheric gases, and is often used in environmental sciences. Each gas has a specific fingerprint due to the absorption of light at discrete wavelengths. In a recent paper in ACPD, under review for ACP, *Angelbratt et al.* [2011] compare both the European and global-scale EMEP model with FTIR measurements at six European stations. A short resumé of the results included in this paper is included here.

In this study model calculated columns of CO and C₂H₆ have been compared to FTIR column data measured at 6 European stations, Jungfrauoch, Zugspitze, Bremen, Harestua, Kiruna and Ny Ålesund (only CO shown here). Model calculations have been made with both the regional and the global version of the Unified EMEP model. Model calculated columns of CO are shown in Fig. 1. An additional tracer calculation is also shown, including only the loss terms for CO. The decay of the tracer gives an indication of the chemical lifetimes for CO. The agreement between the FTIR measurements and the model calculations are better for the global calculations compared to the regional European model calculations, in particular at high latitudes. The overestimation of CO at high latitudes with the regional model is most likely caused by too high concentrations at the lateral boundaries.

Fig. 1. CO partial columns calculated with the global (red triangles) and the regional (blue squares) model versions. The FTIR CO data are shown as black triangles. The solid line shows the calculated CO tracer (Figure from Angelbratt et al. [2011])

The global model is also used to explain the negative trends seen in the measured FTIR CO columns. In the paper it is shown that these trends most likely can be explained by a decrease in the European and North American anthropogenic CO emissions, only partially compensated by an increase in East Asian emissions and an increase resulting from higher methane concentrations and a slight raise in global temperature.

1.2. Source-receptor calculations of short lived climate forcers

Jan Eiof Jonson, Birthe Marie Steensen, and Michael Gauss

Recently, options for mitigation of short-lived climate forcers (SLCF) have received high attention because reducing SLCF might constitute an additional and faster way of abating climate change compared to long lived green-house gases. There is increasing interest in research of SLCF emissions, distribution and effects. Among aerosols, there is general consensus that over bright surfaces, as in the in the Arctic, black carbon (BC), in particular, contributes to climate warming (warming of the lower atmosphere) due to its strong absorption of solar radiation and also by darkening and melting of snow/ice through deposition, thus reducing the planetary albedo. Inevitably, this makes snow- and ice-covered regions like the Arctic most sensitive to BC impacts. Arctic warming also has a global impact through alterations of the general circulation of the atmosphere and the oceans. In addition, reduction of particulate matter, including BC, will benefit public health and is therefore a no-regret option. Less certain are the sign and magnitude of the global radiative forcing associated with BC as the mechanisms by which BC interacts with clouds are poorly understood. In order to design efficient emission mitigation policies, the emission sources and their geographical distribution, and the effects of SLCFs, should be better known. This can only be achieved through a combination of observational methods and model calculations.

In the last years EMEP report [Valiyaveetil, 2010] the EMEP model was applied for SR calculations to study the contributions from European (EMEP) countries to global aerosol loading and aerosol (direct) radiative forcing (RF). In an ongoing project for the Norwegian Ministry of the Environment the global source receptor calculations from last years reporting are extended to also include the effects of sources outside Europe, as world shipping and emissions from countries outside Europe as USA, Canada, China etc. The emissions are based on the RCP (Representative Concentration Pathways) [Moss *et al.*, 2010] 8.5 scenario for 2005. Future scenario runs are also planned for this project. The distribution of the 2005 emissions of EC (elemental carbon) fine and OC organic carbon) fine between different sources/countries is illustrated in Fig. 2. The contributions from these sources to surface concentrations and depositions (dry and wet) of EC in the Arctic (defined as north of 66 degrees) are illustrated in Fig. 3. The contributions to the total columns for EC and POC (Primary Organic Carbon) are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 2. Emissions of EC fine (left) and OC fine (right).

Fig. 3. Left: Contribution to surface concentration of EC fine in the Arctic ($\mu\text{g(C)}$). Right: Contribution to deposition (both dry and wet) of EC fine and in the Arctic ($\mu\text{g(C)}$).

Fig. 4. Contribution to EC fine column (left) and POC column (right) in the Arctic.

The contribution to the Arctic from the different sources is determined by a combination of flow patterns, source strength and proximity to the the Arctic. The allocation of the contributing sources differ with height. The wet part of the deposition will scavenge from the lower middle atmosphere, and the total column will include contributions also from the middle and upper troposphere. As an example emissions from Russia accounts for only about 4% of total fine EC and OC emissions, but contributes by 40% to the model calculated surface concentrations of EC, 26% to EC depositions and 11% to the total column of EC. Even though Chinese emissions account for an estimated 29% of EC fine emissions, these emissions only contributes with 3% to the calculated surface concentrations. The percentage contribution increase substantially with height, and as a result the calculated contribution from Chinese emissions increase to 6% for depositions and 32% for the total column. These results are in agreement with results obtained within the framework of TF HTAP (Task Force on Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution) <http://www.htap.org/> as described in *Shindell et al.* [2008]. However, in TF HTAP Russia was not included as a separate region. Out of the four HTAP regions (Europe, North America, East Asia and South Asia) they found that the largest contribution to the Arctic at the surface was from European sources for CO, BC (Black Carbon) and SO_4 , in particular in the winter and spring months. The dominant contribution from the European and Russian sources in winter can partially be explained by a the high persistence of the Iceland low and the Siberian high pressure system, directing surface flows from the relatively near by European continent into the Arctic. In agreement with this study, *Shindell et al.* [2008] also found that the contributions from East Asian and North American sources increased at higher altitudes (500 and 250 hPa), and that the contribution from in particular East Asian sources were more prominent in summer. However, as also discussed in *Shindell et al.* [2008], the spread in model results is particularly large for advection of pollutants to the Arctic compared to other regions, pointing to substantial uncertainties in the these model results.

1.3. Inclusion of near-term radiative forcing in the GAINS model

Markus Amann, Chris Heyes and Zbigniew Klimont

GAINS model development

The results from the model calculations on short lived radiative forcers presented in (Valiyaveetil, 2010) has been included in the GAINS model. This has required extension of the model to represent emissions of all necessary species, i.e., adding BC, OC, and CO, and introducing respective metrics, i.e, making use of the normalized RF developed by other partners, MSC-W, UiO (University of Oslo), CICERO (Center for International Climate and Environmental Research - Oslo). Table 1 summarizes the current multi-effect/multi-pollutant GAINS framework including the above extension.

Table 1. Multi-pollutant/multi-effect framework of the GAINS model extended to include the impacts on near-term radiative forcing. Note that elements printed in blue are already implemented in the recent GAINS version for Europe while elements in red are introduced within the framework of this project.

	PM (BC, OC)	SO ₂	NO _x	VOC	NH ₃	CO	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O	HFCs PFCs SF ₆
Health impacts:										
PM (Loss in life expectancy)	√	√	√	√	√					
O ₃ (Premature mortality)			√	√		√		√		
Vegetation damage:										
O ₃ (AOT40/fluxes)			√	√		√		√		
Acidification (Excess of critical loads)		√	√		√					
Eutrophication (Excess of critical loads)			√		√					
Climate impacts:										
Long-term (GWP100)	(√)	(√)	(√)	(√)	(√)	(√)	√	√	√	√
Near-term forcing (in Europe and global mean forcing)	√	√	√	√	√	√	(√)	√	(√)	(√)
Black carbon deposition to the arctic	√									

Such a framework, using an extension of the GAINS optimization, focuses only on near-term forcing (together with the air pollution effects), and takes the implications that result from strategies targeted at long-term climate impacts as exogenous boundary conditions. In such a way, decisions on long-lived GHGs that meet long-term climate objectives at the global scale would remain entirely within the UNFCCC framework.

While the optimization considering all additional constraints is still under development, IIASA has developed new BC, OC and CO emission data for the whole EMEP domain (example for 2005 is shown in Fig. 5), implemented the normalized RF, and performed first calculations for the baseline scenario and a control case where only options reducing RF have been selected.

Emissions

IIASA has implemented two scenarios from the IEA World Energy Outlook 2009 [IEA/OECD, 2009] in GAINS (Reference scenario - Baseline CLE; 450 ppm stabilization scenario – 450 ppm) and updated a number of parameters, i.e., PM_{2.5} (including BC and OC) emission factors for diesel vehicles, making use of latest COPERT data, reduction efficiencies for domestic boilers, shipping emission factors, and introduced into GAINS a concept for high-emitting vehicles. Such updated data have been used to prepare and distribute country-specific data sets which were sent for review in June 2010. These sets contained:

Key input data (for domestic and transport sectors)

- Energy data
- Technology shares in different years
- Emission factors of PM_{2.5}, BC and OC

Baseline emission scenario

- Emissions by SNAP sector, including high emitting vehicles
- Emissions by GAINS sectors
- Emissions and implied emission factors by sector-activity for 2005

Responses have been received from DK, FI, NO, CH, UK, and US. In the coming months IIASA will finalize discussions with countries to include the comments.

Fig. 5. Emissions of PM_{2.5}, BC, OC in the UNECE area in 2005; GAINS model estimate

As shown in Fig. 5, the contribution of BC and OC to PM_{2.5} depends on the sector indicating that a successful strategy to reduce BC will have to target sectors with the largest BC/OC ratio first, considering of course impacts on other aerosols. The calculation of the baseline current legislation (CLE) scenario (Fig. 6) shows that emissions of BC are expected to decline, assuming successful implementation of legislation in the transport sector, in the UNECE area. Assuming no change in the technology structure of the residential commercial sector, the climate stabilization scenario (450 ppm) might lead to increased emissions of BC owing to projected growth of biofuel use.

Fig. 6. Emissions of BC in the UNECE area, Baseline CLE scenario by sector and total for 450 ppm scenario; GAINS model estimate

Near-term radiative forcing in GAINS

The EMEP source-receptor results relate changes in grid aerosol column burdens to changes in precursor emissions in individual source countries. In GAINS, the data for the Northern Hemisphere have been combined with the normalized RF factors provided by CICERO to calculate linear transfer coefficients ($\text{Wm}^{-2} \text{kt}^{-1}$) that give the incremental change in area-weighted RF for each component in a given region per kt of pollutant. Initially, the whole Northern Hemisphere, the EMEP region and the Arctic are being considered as receptor regions. By means of the transfer coefficients it is possible in a straightforward way to estimate the influence of each EMEP country on the RF in these regions (for those aspects of RF included in this assessment) for any particular emissions scenario.

By way of illustration, Fig. 7 shows the impact of emissions of 1000 tons of BC on instantaneous forcing over the Northern Hemisphere, EMEP domain and Arctic, defined as the area above 70°N . Red marks indicate Arctic Council countries, showing their growing relative importance when the domain is reduced to Arctic.

IIASA has also developed a first control scenario beyond CLE. This scenario assumes the selection of options for which the RF value is lower than for the no-control situation considering all co-emitted species. The selection was made using global warming potentials (GWP 100) from IPCC AR4 and other, more recent, peer reviewed sources which provided estimates of warming potential for aerosols and gases (see Table 2). The scenario includes the following key control categories:

- EURO VI (including Diesel Particulate Filters [DPF]) on road and non-road machinery
- Pellet stoves
- End of pipe in industry and small commercial and residential boilers

Fig. 8 illustrates the impact of this scenario on forcing over the Arctic region along with the comparable calculations performed for the year 2005 and for the baseline scenario (CLE).

Fig. 7. Impact on instantaneous forcing of 1 kt BC over different domains; Marked regions include Arctic Council countries (red) and two sea regions (green) – Baltic Sea and North Sea, $mW m^{-2} kt BC^{-1}$; Source: EMEP/MS-CW

Table 2. GWPs used for screening of mitigation measures

	GWP 100 (mean)	Range	Source
CO ₂	1		IPCC-AR4, 2007
CH ₄	25	16 to 34	IPCC-AR4, 2007
SO ₂	-40	-24 to -56	Fuglestvedt et al., 2009; Schulz et al., 2006
CO	1.9	1 to 3	IPCC-AR3, cited in AR4, 2007
BC	680	210 to 1500	Bond and Sun, 2005
OC	-69	-35 to -104	Schulz et al., 2006; Bond & Sun, 2005
NMVOC	3.4	2 to 7	IPCC-AR4, 2007 (ref to Collins et al., 2002)
NO _x	~ 0		

Further work is currently under-way to extend the GAINS optimization framework by employing the RF transfer coefficients and related data in that module, so that near-term radiative forcing can be addressed within the optimization process – in addition to the existing health and environmental impacts – either as an extra constraint or in a multi-objective fashion.

Fig. 8. Country contributions to forcing over the Arctic domain (>70° N).

1.4. Sensitivity tests perturbing the pH value and wet deposition rates

Jan Eiof Jonson

Model validation from previous years have shown a growing bias in model calculated sulphur species compared to measurements (see <http://emep.int> for reports from previous years). In the course of the last decades there has been substantial decreases in anthropogenic emissions in Europe and North America, and in particular so for sulphur. No doubt this has also changed the cloud acidity. It is not straight forward to calculate incloud acidity, as it require knowledge about base cations not included in the model calculations. In present versions of the Unified EMEP model the pH value has been fixed at about 4.3. As a sensitivity test we have changed the pH value to 5. This will affect the incloud oxidation of SO₂ to sulphate by ozone and O₂ catalysed by metal ions. Even though these reactions are independent on pH, the uptake of SO₂ in droplets is not, making the overall reaction pH dependent.

Wet deposition from ice clouds is very uncertain, but it is believed to be significantly less than from liquid clouds. Presently no distinction is made between scavenging by liquid water and ice clouds. As a sensitivity test we have reduced wet scavenging below cloud to 5% when temperatures drop below 273K, and to 20% for incloud scavenging when temperatures drop below 260K.

In the Figs. 9 to 12 the effects of these sensitivity test are compared to the reference model run. The effects of reducing the wet scavenging in and below ice clouds result in increases in sulphur (both SO₂ and sulphate), in particular at high latitudes, where temperatures are low (Fig. 9 and 10, left). Wet depositions decrease near the source regions, but increase further away from the source regions as sulphur is advected further Fig. 11, left).

At higher latitudes H₂O₂ is less abundant, in particular in winter. As a result in the model oxidation will only proceed via ozone or O₂ catalysed by metal ions. With pH levels increased to 5, these oxidation pathways becomes faster, resulting in a decrease in SO₂ levels (Fig. 9, right) and an increase in sulphate (Fig. 10, right) and sulphate wet deposition (Fig. 11, right).

With lower efficiency in the wet deposition total nitrate levels are anti-correlated with sulphate. With higher/lower levels less/more ammonium will be available forming ammonium nitrate which has a longer residence time in the atmosphere than gas phase HNO₃. As a result total nitrate concentrations decrease in the source regions (where sulphate levels are higher), and increase in remote areas Fig. 12, left). The increase in pH values has only minor effects on total nitrate (Fig. 12, right).

Model results for SO₂, sulphate and NO₃ are also discussed in the next chapter, in connection with the implementation of the model results in the AEROCOM tool.

Fig. 9. Percentage change in surface SO₂ levels as a result of perturbing the wet deposition (left) and both wet deposition and the incloud pH value (right).

Fig. 10. Percentage change in surface sulphate levels as a result of perturbing the wet deposition (left) and both wet deposition and the incloud pH value (right).

Fig. 11. Percentage change in sulphur deposition as a result of perturbing the wet deposition (left) and both wet deposition and the incloud pH value (right).

Fig. 12. Percentage change in surface total nitrate levels as a result of perturbing the wet deposition (left) and both wet deposition and the incloud pH value (right).

1.5. Inclusion of the model results in the AEROCOM tool

Jan Eiof Jonson, Jan Griesfeller and Michael Schulz

Model results from the Unified EMEP model are now included in the AEROCOM tool. AEROCOM (<http://nansen.ipsl.jussieu.fr/AEROCOM>) is an open international initiative of scientists interested in the advancement of the understanding of the global aerosol and its impact on climate. A large number of observations and results from many, mostly global models, have been assembled to document and compare state of the art modelling of the global aerosol. Maps, statistics, histograms, bias maps, scatter plots and simple scores are produced by an automated idl tool. In-situ surface observations in AEROCOM are mainly from NILU based EBAS database (<http://ebas.nilu.no/>).

Figs. 13 and 14 shows the model to measurement bias of SO₂, sulphate, NO₃ and wet deposition of sulphur for the model version testing the effects of reduced wet deposition in ice clouds and increased pH levels as described in the previous chapter. Compared to the reference model version the model to measurements bias has improved, but other statistics such as correlation and RMS error, show no improvement or a slight decline in quality. More research is needed in order to improve the model performance here. The Figs. 13 and 14 reveal that there are substantial regional differences between Europe, North America and East Asia in model to measurement bias. We have yet to explain the source of these regional differences. However, in particular for sulphur, emissions have changed substantially in recent years, and it may be that the emissions used do not fully reflect these changes.

Fig. 13. Model bias in percent for SO₂ (a) and sulphate (b)

Fig. 14. Model bias in percent for NO₃ (a) and wet deposition of sulphur (b).

2. DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION OF THE GLEMOS MODELLING FRAMEWORK

The global modelling framework GLEMOS has been developed in MSC-E for last years to extend the scope of heavy metal and POP assessment to a global scale and to elaborate a consistent approach for multi-scale simulations in Europe. Progress of the framework development and evaluation was described in a number of recent technical reports [Tarrasón and Gusev, 2008; Travnikov et al., 2009; Jonson and Travnikov, 2010]. The formulated requirements to the modelling framework include a flexible choice of the model domain and grid resolution, multi-pollutant and multi-media approaches, a modular architecture and computational efficiency of the modelling. The modular architecture is one of the key features of the framework and it is aimed to provide flexibility for simulation of pollutants with diverse properties.

The general scheme of the framework reflecting the modular architecture is presented in Fig. 15. Each environmental medium is presented in the model by a set of procedures describing general processes in the medium which are combined into the program modules. Each module can be attached to or detached from the model at the compilation stage using command scripts. All pollutants are combined in groups of substances with similar properties (e.g. mercury, particulate heavy metals, POPs etc.). Each pollutant group is presented in the model by a number of modules defining the pollutant properties and its behaviour in each environmental media. Besides, each pollutant can be

Fig. 15. General scheme of the modular architecture of the GLEMOS modeling framework

characterized by different physical forms or chemical compounds specific for each media. The pollutant groups can be attached to the model using the procedure similar to that for the environmental media.

Three major groups of substances have been included into the current version of the framework: mercury, particle-bound heavy metals (Pb, Cd) and POPs. An additional pollutant group (not shown in the figure) that is mainly used for testing and evaluation of the model performance pertains to inert and radioactive tracers (^{131}I , ^{134}Cs , ^{137}Cs , ^{132}Te , etc.) It is also planned to include a separate group of modules for simulation of atmospheric aerosol to improve the model description of heavy metal and POP related atmospheric processes (gas-particle partitioning, sorption, heterogeneous chemistry, etc.)

A consistent multi-media approach has been developed for POPs previously [Gusev et al., 2005] and it has been adapted for appropriate media modules of GLEMOS including the atmosphere, ocean, and terrestrial media. Current version of the framework includes only the atmospheric modules for mercury and particulate heavy metal groups. Other media modules for

these substances are planned to be developed using approaches tested in the low-resolution version of the model [Travnikov *et al.*, 2009].

Significant efforts were undertaken this year to improve and further develop meteorological and oceanic pre-processors required for input data support of the model simulations on a global scale. In addition, the oceanic transport module describing pollution dispersion in the ocean with sea currents has been re-designed and thoroughly tested. Besides, the mercury atmospheric chemistry modules were updated and evaluated against measurements. These new model developments are discussed below.

2.1. Adaptation and testing of WRF as a meteorological driver for multi-scale modelling

Alexey Gusev

This section describes the progress in the evaluation of meteorological drivers for the GLEMOS modelling system which is aimed at the harmonization of meteorological input for global scale modelling within EMEP. The evaluation of meteorological drivers, namely, IFS, GEM, and WRF, performed in the EMEP Centres, is covered in the reports [Tarrasón and Gusev, 2008; Travnikov *et al.*, 2009]. In course of this work it was revealed that selected models (IFS, GEM) had satisfactory performance to be used as the meteorological drivers for the EMEP global modelling. In addition, both Centres have started evaluation of the WRF model as a potential candidate for the common meteorological driver. Advanced research version of the WRF model has a number of important features for the application in pre-processing of meteorological data, namely, wide range of physical parameterizations, multi-scale modelling capabilities, assimilation of measurements, and availability of coupled version for atmospheric chemistry and aerosol dynamics modelling (WRF-Chem). This year the adaptation of WRF was continued with testing its updated version 3.3. WRF model output was compared with the data of the previously tested GEM model and available measurements of different meteorological parameters.

Model setup and data used for testing

To evaluate performance of the new version of WRF global scale simulations were carried out by MSC-E for January and July 2001, in line with the previous stage of the work [Travnikov *et al.*, 2009]. The modelling was performed on the domain with the lat-lon grid using horizontal resolution $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ and 20 layers along the vertical with upper boundary at 10hPa.

The following parameterizations of physical processes were selected for global-scale WRF model simulations:

Microphysics	<i>Morrison 2-moment;</i>
Longwave Radiation	<i>RRTM;</i>
Shortwave Radiation	<i>Dudhia;</i>
Surface Layer	<i>ETA similarity;</i>
Land Surface	<i>5-layer thermal diffusion;</i>
Planetary Boundary Level	<i>Mellor-Yamada-Janjic scheme;</i>
Cumulus	<i>Kain-Fritsch.</i>

Generation of meteorological input for GLEMOS model was organized as a sequence of short 36-h runs with 12-h spin-up. Along these short 36-h periods WRF was run with three-dimensional data assimilation over the whole simulation period. For the driving input and assimilation the data of ECMWF analyses for 2001 were used.

Discussion of results

To evaluate the performance of WRF (version 3.3) two output variables were considered and compared with the GEM modelling results and measurements, namely, near-surface air temperature and precipitation amount. Spatial distribution of monthly mean air temperature obtained in the simulations of the WRF and GEM for January and July of 2001 is shown in Fig. 16. Both models predicted similar patterns of near-surface air temperature. Some differences can be seen between the modelling results for July in the Arctic where the WRF provided slightly higher temperatures in comparison with GEM.

Fig. 16. Spatial distribution of monthly mean air temperature (°C) at 2 m for January and July 2001 calculated by the WRF and GEM models

Modelling results of WRF were compared with RAOB (Radiosonde Database - <http://raob.fsl.noaa.gov>) and GSN (GCOS Surface Network – <http://www.gosic.org/gcos/GSN-data-access.htm>) measurements and with corresponding results of the GEM model. Brief statistical analysis of the WRF and GEM modelling results and measurements of near-surface air temperature at the RAOB sites for January and July 2001 is presented in Table 3. Both models showed close values comparing to measured

The comparison of monthly precipitation amount calculated by the GEM and WRF models versus the measurements of the GSN network for January and July 2001 has shown reasonable agreement as between the models and also with measurements (Table 4). The spatial correlation of measured and calculated precipitation amount in January 2001 is about 0.7 for both models. It can be seen that the WRF results for January slightly better agree with measurements comparing to the GEM results. In case of July 2001 WRF provided on average slightly higher precipitation amount than measured, which is connected with the overestimation of measurements at some sites by the model, and lower correlation compared to GEM.

Table 4. Monthly precipitation site averages (mm/month) and correlation coefficients (R_{corr}) calculated on the basis of WRF and GEM modelling results and measurements of precipitation obtained at GSN sites for January and July 2001.

Month	Monthly precipitation amount (site average)			R_{corr}	
	Measured	Calculated by WRF	Calculated by GEM	WRF	GEM
January	73	71	66	0.74	0.73
July	81	94	82	0.65	0.71

An updated version of the research WRF model was adapted and tested as a meteorological driver for the global modelling framework GLEMOS. Global scale modelling results of WRF for air temperature and precipitation were compared with RAOB and GSN measurements and with the corresponding results of the GEM model tested earlier. The model demonstrated good agreement with available measurements as well as with the results of GEM.

Further steps in adaptation and testing of WRF will include preparation of meteorological input for multi-scale modeling and for experimental simulations to explore the effects of climate change on air pollution. Besides, its coupled version WRF-Chem can be used as an additional source of information on spatial and temporal variations of atmospheric constituents (aerosol and reactants) required in global and regional scale modelling of heavy metals and POPs.

2.2. Oceanological driver for the GLEMOS modelling framework

Valeriy Sokovykh

Multi-media simulations of pollutants dispersion in the environment require gridded oceanological input data (sea currents, water temperature, salinity, etc.) In order to prepare self-consistent datasets Parallel Ocean Program (<http://climate.lanl.gov/Models/POP/>) was chosen as the oceanic pre-processor for the GLEMOS model. This is a freely available model developed at Los Alamos National Laboratory. The POP model is derived from the Bryan-Cox-Semtner class of ocean models [Semtner, 1986] first developed by Kirk Bryan and Michael Cox at the NOAA. POP is the ocean component of the Community Climate System Model - CESM (<http://www.cesm.ucar.edu/>) - a fully-coupled, global climate model that provides state-of-the-art computer simulations of the Earth's past, present, and future climate states.

The POP model has been adapted, spinned-up and tested. This section is devoted to the description of adaptation and use of the POP model at MSCE.

Grids and bathymetry

The POP model was compiled and launched at the MSC-E on a global scale with $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ and $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolutions. The data with $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ resolution is supposed to be used as input information for long-term historical computations of POP cycling aimed at spin-up and preparation of input data for $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ modelling.

The vertical structure of the model grid chosen for both $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ and $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolutions is shown on Fig. 18. Fifteen irregular layers are used and their boundaries are coincide with the appropriate boundaries of the 29-layer ECMWF ORA-S3 ocean re-analysis for better data assimilation.

Fig. 18. 15-layer vertical structure of POP ocean model

Gridded bathymetry data sets have been compiled on the base of the following two information sources:

1. ISLSCP2 $\frac{1}{4}$ degree dataset (http://daac.ornl.gov/ISLSCP_II/islscpii.shtml): land-ocean mask (Fig. 19).
2. ETOPO2v2 global gridded 2-minute database (<http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/global/etopo2.html>): global relief (Fig. 20).

Fig. 19. $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ land-ocean mask based on ISLSCP2 data

Fig. 20. $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ global relief based on ETOPO2v2 data

Spin-up

To initialize global-scale oceanic calculations monthly climatological data on potential temperature and water salinity were used (NOAA NODC World Ocean Atlas 2005: http://www.nodc.noaa.gov/OC5/WOA05/pr_woa05.html). The velocity field was set to zero at the start of computations. The spin-up period is the time taken by an ocean model to reach a state of statistical equilibrium under the applied forcing. Usually, it is extremely time consuming for global general circulation models to reach this state. The deep ocean requires hundreds of years to adjust. The upper ocean requires about 50-100 years. Therefore, we have performed 200-years spin-up for the $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ grid and 100-years one – for the $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid.

Mean kinetic energy (KE) of water is traditionally used as an indicator of the statistical equilibrium. Figure 21 shows time trends of the total mean KE and the KE of the upper water layer during spin-up periods for the $1^0 \times 1^0$ and $3^0 \times 3^0$ resolutions. It can be seen that the upper ocean reached the quasi-steady state earlier than the deep ocean. Kinetic energy depends on the grid resolution, but the curves look similar. Vertical profiles of KE are presented in Fig. 22a. The energy of the upper ocean is many times greater than that of the lower ocean.

Fig. 21. Mean kinetic energy for $1^0 \times 1^0$ and $3^0 \times 3^0$ spin-up runs for the upper model layer (right vertical axis) and for all the layers (left axis)

Fig. 22. Vertical profiles of mean KE during 200-year spin-up on climatological data (a) and after 15-year spin-up on re-analysis (b). Data for $3^0 \times 3^0$ grid.

The result of the spin-up on climatological data is a set of statistically balanced gridded variables which could be used for subsequent short-term simulations. It should be noted that the field of currents velocity (Fig. 23) has been formed by the gravity and the Coriolis force. Wind stress and other surface meteorological parameters (atmospheric pressure and temperature) were not taken into account. For this reason, velocity and temperature fields (Fig. 24) are smooth and slowly changing. To take into consideration the friction between wind and the water's surface in consistency with the influence of other surface meteorological parameters (atmospheric pressure and temperature) it is needed to force the model variables by high temporal resolution analysis data. The ECMWF 6-hour meteorological re-analysis (<http://www.ecmwf.int/>) was used for this purpose at the second stage of the spin-up (Fig. 25). In addition to this, daily 3-D data on the ocean potential temperature and salinity from ECMWF ORA S3 ocean re-analyses were assimilated at this stage. The inclusion of new data required several years to establish the new equilibrium, characterized by high level of KE in the upper ocean (Fig. 22b).

Fig. 23. Spatial distributions of zonal (a) and meridional (b) current velocities (cm/s) in the upper ocean layer after 100-year spin-up with $1^0 \times 1^0$ spatial resolution

Fig. 24. Spatial distributions of potential temperature (degrees C) in the upper ocean layer after 100-year spin-up with $1^0 \times 1^0$ spatial resolution

Results for 2009

Pre-processing of the ocean parameters for the GLEMOS model has been carried out as the last phase of the whole computation cycle using forcing by the ECMWF data (Fig. 8). The $1^0 \times 1^0$ and $3^0 \times 3^0$ datasets for 2009 have been prepared. To evaluate the performance of POP model and reliability of these data the ocean current fields were analyzed. Sea currents velocity was not assimilated from the analysis. For this reason, it can be used as independent measure of data quality assessment.

Fig. 25. Calculation cycle of the POPs model

The spatial distributions of currents velocity components and potential temperature in the upper ocean layer (Fig. 26) are much more variable than those obtained without the wind stress influence (Fig. 23, 24). The major currents (Equatorial, Gulf Stream, Kuroshio, Antarctic Circumpolar etc.) were reproduced by the model. Summer distributions of oceanic parameters are quite different from the winter ones.

Fig. 26. Spatial distributions of zonal and meridional current velocities (cm/s) and potential temperature (degrees C) in the upper ocean layer on 31 Jul and 31 Dec 2009

Fig. 27. Scatter plot for annual mean calculated and measured ocean current velocities

Calculated ocean currents have been compared with fixed depth measurement data of Tropical Atmosphere Ocean (TAO) project (<http://www.pmel.noaa.gov/tao/>). 33 of 39 TAO measurement sites were involved in the comparison. 5 sites were excluded due to insufficient number of measurements, 1 site – due to very strong variations of currents in the vertical direction which could not be reproduced by 15-layer model. Annual mean modeled ($1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$) and measured values at 10m depth are in good agreement (Fig. 27). Daily computed data for most of the stations correlates with measurements (Fig. 28 - an example for equatorial station in the Indian Ocean).

Fig. 28. Calculated and measured daily averaged zonal ocean current velocities (cm/s) in the Indian Ocean (0° N, 80.5° E) at depth 10 m

2.3. Development and testing of the oceanic transport module

Valeriy Sokovykh

As noted above, the Parallel Ocean Program (POP) model was chosen as the oceanic pre-processor for the GLEMOS model. The POP model provides a means of modelling the advection and diffusion of passive tracers in the ocean. The modelling of passive tracers oceanic transport is performing using similar methods that are used for the main ocean parameters such as temperature, salinity and currents velocity. It is reasonable to employ the same numerical methods and the discretization for the description of oceanic tracer transport in the GLEMOS model to ensure the compatibility of the models and to provide better adaptation of input data.

The numerical scheme of advection and diffusion used in the POP model was implemented into the oceanic module of the GLEMOS model (which also contains partitioning, degradation and sedimentation modules) and tested. Below a brief description of the scheme and some results of the testing of the new GLEMOS oceanic transport module are presented.

Numerical scheme of tracer oceanic transport

Transport equation

The following form of tracer transport equation is currently used in the POP model:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(1 + \xi)\psi + L(\psi) = D_H(\psi) + D_V(\psi) + F(\psi), \quad (1)$$

where ψ is the tracer concentration,

$(1 + \xi)$ is the change in volume of the surface layer due to undulations of the free surface

($\xi = 0$ for all other layers),

L is the advection operator,

D_H, D_V are the horizontal and vertical diffusion operators, respectively,

F is the change in tracer concentration associated with the tracer surface flux.

Spatial discretization

Staggered horizontal Arakawa-B grid is used in horizontal planes: scalars are defined at cell centers and vectors – at cell corners. Vertical component of velocity is normal to cell faces. (Fig. 29).

Finite-difference approximation of L , D_H and D_V operators can be found in [Smith and Gent, 2002].

Time discretization

The POP model uses a 3-time-level second order accurate modified leapfrog scheme for stepping forward in time. The discrete analogue of (1) is:

$$(1 + \xi^{n+1})\psi^{n+1} - (1 + \xi^{n-1})\psi^{n-1} = 2\Delta t \left[-L_T^a(\psi^n) + D_H(\psi^{n-1}) + D_V(\psi^\lambda) + F^n \right], \quad (2)$$

where $\psi^\lambda = \lambda\psi^{n+1} + (1-\lambda)\psi^{n-1}$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$.

The procedure called “averaging timestep” is employed periodically to prevent $2\Delta t$ oscillations in time due to the partial decoupling of the even and odd timesteps.

Horizontal velocity components, diffusivity coefficients, surface tracer flux and surface layer depth are input data for the equation (2). Vertical velocity is determined from the solution of the continuity equation.

Testing results

Several simple one- and two-dimensional tests have been performed. In addition, three-dimensional tracer simulation has been carried out. In all of the test it was supposed that $\xi = 0$ and $F = 0$. The frequency for applying averaging procedure was chosen equal to 17 timesteps.

Diffusion test

One-dimensional diffusion of function $\psi(x, t)$ with original distribution:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x,0) &= \psi_0 & -l \leq x \leq l \\ \psi(x,0) &= 0 & x < -l, \quad x > l \end{aligned}$$

was investigated. All the three directions (vertical and two horizontal) have been examined. Calculation results were compared with the exact solution:

$$\psi(x, t) = \frac{\psi_0}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} \int_{-l}^l \exp\left(-\frac{(x-x')^2}{4Dt}\right) dx',$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient.

Fig. 29. The 3-D grid cell showing the location of velocity components (u, v, w) and tracer concentration (ψ)

Some results for spatial step $\Delta x = 0.1l$ and timestep $\Delta t = 0.01 \frac{l^2 D}{\psi_0}$ are presented in Fig. 30. It can be seen that calculations are close to the theory. The implicit vertical diffusion scheme (red lines) gives more precise results than the explicit horizontal one (blue lines), especially at the end of the period.

Fig. 30. Calculated and theoretical temporal (a) and spatial (b) profiles of diffusive function $\psi(x,t)$

Rotational flow field test

Rotational flow experiment for an advection numerical scheme first proposed by Smolarkiewicz [1982] has been carried out in Cartesian and lat-lon coordinates.

a. Cartesian coordinates

A cone with the base radius $15\Delta x$ and the maximum height $\psi_{\max_0} = \sqrt{15\Delta x}$ was originally located in a background field $\psi_0 = 1$ in two-dimensional domain of 200×200 grid points with $\Delta x = \Delta y = 1$. The cone was rotated with constant angular velocity $\omega = 0.1$ clockwise around the point $(100\Delta x, 150\Delta y)$. (Fig. 31a). The integration was carried out with a timestep $\Delta t = 0.05$. The test has shown that numerical diffusion of the scheme is not very high (Fig. 31, 32). After one full rotation the cone became 14% lower. Its form was somewhat disturbed. Low-amplitude wavelike disturbance of the background field took place on the leeward side of the cone (Fig. 32).

Fig. 31. Initial conditions (a) and results (b) of rotational field flow test. Concentric circles denote isolines of ψ value with step $\Delta\psi=0.5$ after $1/4$ of full revolution (1), $1/2$ of full revolution (2), $3/4$ of full revolution (3), full revolution (4)

Fig. 32. Spatial distributions of ψ value in rotational field flow test: a – initial, b – after one full rotation

b. Latitude-longitude coordinates

The same test was carried out on the $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ latitude-longitude grid. The center of rotation was placed on the equator. A cone with the radius $\pi R_e / 180$ (R_e is the radius of the Earth) and height $\psi_{\max_0} = \sqrt{15}$ began to rotate in a background field $\psi_0 = 1$ from the initial point located at latitude $\varphi = 45^\circ$ and the same longitude as the rotational center ($\Delta\lambda = 0$). The components of rotation velocity for this case was defined as:

$$V_\varphi = -\omega R_e \sin(\Delta\lambda)$$

$$V_\lambda = \omega R_e |\cos(\Delta\lambda)| \sin \varphi$$

where $\omega = 2\pi \text{ min}^{-1}$ – the angular velocity.

The results of the integration with a timestep $\Delta t = 0.05$ (Fig. 33) are similar to those in Cartesian coordinates. The cone height reduction was the same 14%.

Fig. 33. Initial conditions (a) and results (b) of rotational field flow test. Concentric circles denote isolines of ψ value after $1/4$ of full revolution (1), $1/2$ of full revolution (2), $3/4$ of full revolution (3), full revolution (4)

Deformational flow field test

Deformational-flow two-dimensional test suggested by *Smolarkiewicz* [2002] has been performed. A cone with radius $15\Delta x$ and maximum height $\psi_{\max_0} = \sqrt{15\Delta x}$ relative to the spatially constant background value $\psi_0 = 1$ was initially located in the center of the domain (Fig. 34) with $\Delta x = \Delta y = 1$ in the field of symmetrical deforming vortices. The velocities in x and y directions were given as:

$$u = \frac{8\pi}{25} \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{25}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{25}\right),$$

$$v = \frac{8\pi}{25} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{25}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi y}{25}\right)$$

The integration time step was $\Delta t = 0.7$.

The results of the experiment are presented in Fig. 35. The background field outside the central vortices remained weakly perturbed during the integration and not much different from the initial value $\psi_0 = 1$. The maximum of ψ -distribution inside the central vortices decreased in time and reached steady-state value $\psi_{\max} = 0.35\psi_{\max_0}$. The highest values within each of two central vortices after 10000 iterations were found near the boundaries rather than at the center, which corresponds to the analytical solution. So, the scheme is relatively stable to the deformational flows.

Fig. 34. Scheme of deformational flow test. Isolines of ψ -function are marked in red. Arrows denote velocity vectors.

Fig. 35. Results of deformational flow field test. ψ -distributions: a – initial, b – after 19 iterations, c – after 38 iterations, d – after 75 iterations, e – after 10000 iterations.

Tracer test

Annual calculation of a tracer ocean transport in the real field of currents (calculated by the POP model for 2009) has been performed. It was supposed that four point sources located near the coast of the USA, Italy, Japan, and Nigeria released tracer to the upper ocean layer with constant rate. Tracer was assumed to be diphasic: dissolved and particulate phases were considered. The following oceanic processes were examined: advection, vertical and horizontal diffusion, partitioning, degradation, and sedimentation. The properties of tracer related to these processes were supposed the same as that of PCB-153. The exchange with other media was neglected.

Spatial distributions of the tracer water concentration for two time moments in the middle and at the end of the year are presented in Fig. 36. It can be seen that tracer was transported from the sources relatively slowly. For example, being released in Gulf Stream, it did not reach the European coast by the end of the year (Fig. 36b). Most of tracer mass remained in the upper ocean during all the period of simulation (Fig. 37).

Almost the entire released tracer mass was preserved in the ocean. Only 1 percent degraded. The share of sedimented mass was negligible.

Fig. 36. Tracer test results. Spatial distributions of tracer ocean concentrations in the upper model layer on Jul 31 (a) and Dec 31 (b). Units: percent of the maximum value on Dec 31.

Fig. 37. Tracer test results. Spatial distributions of tracer ocean concentrations in vertical plane located at 40° N on Jul 31 (a) and Dec 31 (b). Units: percent of the maximum value on Dec 31. Solid lines denote levels 0.01%, 1%, 10%. Tracer released near the coast of the USA (75° W, 35.5° N).

2.4. Multi-media simulations of POPs on a global scale

Valeriy Sokovykh

Fig. 38. The scheme of the main processes related to POPs in the current version of the GLEMOS model (the dissolved phase includes also POPs sorbed on the dissolved organic matter)

After the implementation of the new ocean module the scheme of the main processes related to persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the current GLEMOS version assumed the form shown in Fig. 38. Several phases of POPs (rectangles) are considered in each medium. These phases are involved in different physical-chemical processes (highlighted blue), namely, transport, degradation, phase partitioning, and inter-media exchange (arrows).

To evaluate the capability of GLEMOS to reproduce POPs environmental contamination levels at the current stage of model development an annual global-scale simulation of PCB-153 transport on the $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ grid was performed. Spin-up from 1970 on the $3^{\circ} \times 3^{\circ}$ grid was employed. Historical emissions compiled on the basis of “maximum” and “default” scenarios of the global inventory were used [Breivik et al., 2007]. Some of the results are presented below to illustrate the actual state of the art.

The atmosphere. The spatial distribution of annual mean air concentration of PCB-153 in the lowest model layer is presented in Fig. 39. Elevated level of contamination is a characteristic of the Europe and North America. In the most polluted central part of Europe air concentrations exceed 4 pg/m^3 . Over the most part of the Southern Hemisphere PCB-153 air concentrations are relatively low ($0.1\text{-}0.3 \text{ pg/m}^3$).

The results of modelling were compared to measurement data on PCB-153 concentrations in air at the EMEP monitoring network. Annual and monthly mean concentrations were considered. Some results are presented in Figs. 40 and 41.

The model reproduces contamination levels of PCB-153 in the EMEP region (Fig. 40). Annual mean site averaged modeled value (1.50 pg/m^3) is very close to measured one (1.55 pg/m^3). There is high spatial correlation of annual mean modeled and measured concentrations in air. The coefficient of linear correlation equals to 0.88.

Fig. 39. Spatial distributions of PCB-153 annual mean concentration in surface air for 2009

Fig.40. Annual mean PCB-153 concentrations in air calculated by the GLEMOS model and measured at the EMEP monitoring sites in 2009

The temporal changes of monthly mean air concentrations of PCB-153 are in accordance with measurements for most of the EMEP sites. Figure 41 presents examples for two stations: Swedish site SE14 and Czech site CZ03. In many cases the model has reproduced most of the peculiarities of measured time trend (SE14). Nevertheless, in some cases the correlation of monthly mean concentrations is not very high (CZ03).

Fig. 41. Monthly mean PCB-153 concentrations in air calculated by the GLEMOS model and measured at the EMEP monitoring sites SE14 (a) and CZ03 (b) in 2009

The ocean. The field of PCB-153 concentrations in the surface layer of seawater is given in Fig. 42. There is evident latitudinal dependence of pollution level. The highest values of PCB-153 content in seawater (more than 0.5 pg/L) were obtained for high-latitude regions. The reason for this is strong temperature dependence of the gaseous flux from air to water: lower air temperatures correspond to higher air-water flux. Seawater PCB-153 concentrations in the Antarctic region are higher than those in equatorial regions.

Fig. 42. Spatial distributions of PCB-153 annual mean concentration in seawater for 2009, pg/L

Fig. 43. Zonally averaged meridional profiles of measured and modelled PCB-153 concentrations in seawater, pg/L

Measurement data on PCB-153 concentrations in seawater from different campaigns [AMAP, 1998; AMAP, 2004; Schulz-Bull et al., 1991; Iwata et al., 1993; Kannan et al., 1998; PWGSC, 2003] were employed for the validation of the oceanic module of GLEMOS. For the comparison with calculation results for 2009 observations related to different years were scaled in accordance with the time trend of PCB-153 total ocean mass content [Jonson and Travníkov, 2010]. In addition to this, observations were divided into three groups according to latitude of measurement sites and zonally averaged within groups. The groups were as follows:

- 40° North: Japan Sea;
- 50° North: North Sea, Bering Sea;
- 70° North: Norwegian Sea, Barents Sea, Beaufort Sea, Chukchi Sea.

As it is seen from Fig. 42, the model has reproduced measured latitudinal trend of PCB-153 content in seawater as a whole.

Soil. Figure 43 shows global-scale spatial distribution of calculated annual mean PCB-153 concentrations in the top 5 cm of soil. Elevated levels of PCB-153 in soil occurred in the regions with maximum anthropogenic emissions: they are Europe and Northern America. Maximum concentrations (over 100 pg/g) take place in the Central Europe. The range 20-70 pg/g can be assumed as a background for Europe, 3-10 pg/g – for North America.

Modelled concentrations of PCB-153 in upper soil level for 2009 have been compared with surface soil measurements of PCB-153/132 performed at 191 background sites worldwide in 1998 [Meijer *et al.*, 2003]. To reduce significant dispersion of the observational data, they were grouped the following way: the series of measurements related to one and the same cell was replaced by the arithmetic mean of these measurements. The resulting scatter plot of observed and calculated soil concentrations is given in Fig. 44. In general, measured values exceed calculated ones substantially. High vertical gradient of PCB-153 soil concentration near ground surface seems the main reason for this: maximum levels of concentration can not be reproduced by the model due to limited vertical spatial resolution of the model grid. Another reason is reducing of PCB-153 content in all the media due to threefold decrease of anthropogenic emissions from 1998 to 2009 [Breivik *et al.*, 2007]. At the same time, there is good correlation between measured and modelled values in logarithmic scale. Taking into account significant scatter of the observed soil concentrations, the results of the comparison can be considered as reasonable.

Fig. 43. Spatial distributions of PCB-153 annual mean concentration in the top 5 cm of soil for 2009

Fig. 44. Scatter plot of calculated soil concentrations of PCB-153 in the upper soil level and measured soil concentrations of PCB-153/132 [Meijer *et al.*, 2003] (*dw* – dry weight of soil)

It can be concluded that simulations of PCB-153 global transport revealed the consistency of calculated air concentrations with measurements of the EMEP monitoring network. In general, the computed concentrations in the upper soil and seawater surface layer are in a reasonable agreement with available measurements.

Thus, three environmental media have been included in the GLEMOS model by now: the atmosphere, the ocean and soil. The global-scale modelling of POP fate in the ocean with sea currents, diffusion, degradation, and sedimentation processes are available. Nevertheless, further improvement of the multi-media approach within the GLEMOS modelling system is required. Particularly, the description of POP fate in vegetation and the interaction of this compartment with the atmosphere and soil is needed.

2.5. Evaluation of GLEMOS mercury simulations on a global scale

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Mercury component of the GLEMOS modelling framework has been developed for last years in MSC-E. The physical and chemical modules for mercury were based on the previous well developed and tested hemispheric model MSCE-Hg-Hem [Travnikov, 2005]. Progress in elaboration and application of the mercury component of the framework was outline in previous technical reports [Travnikov *et al.*, 2009; Jonson and Travnikov, 2010]. In addition, it also took part in the multi-model experiments performed within the TF HTAP Assessment 2010 [HTAP, 2010]. This year the mercury chemical scheme of the framework has been refined and applied for simulations of mercury transport on a global scale. The modelling results were thoroughly evaluated against measurements collected from both available monitoring networks and a literature survey.

Recent studies have demonstrated that chemical oxidation of Hg by reactive halogen species (primarily Br and BrO) may essentially affect or even determine the mercury cycle in the atmosphere, in particular, in the polar regions [Steffen *et al.*, 2008; Ebinghaus *et al.*, 2002]. As it was observed in the Arctic and Antarctica, during springtime Hg⁰ concentration episodically depleted to very low concentrations owing to fast transformation to short lived oxidized forms with subsequent deposition to the surface [Lindberg *et al.*, 2002; Aria *et al.*, 2004; Skov *et al.*, 2004]. This phenomenon, termed as the Atmospheric Mercury Depletion Events (AMDE), leads to a considerable increase in total mercury deposition in the polar regions. However, a considerable proportion of deposited Hg is rapidly photoreduced in snowpack and re-emitted to the atmosphere [Kirk *et al.*, 2006; Johnson *et al.*, 2008; Ferrari *et al.*, 2008].

The mechanism of AMDEs has been implemented into the GLEMOS modelling framework and tested on a global scale [Jonson and Travnikov, 2010]. In particular, the reactions of Hg⁰ oxidation by atomic Br and BrO in the Arctic and Antarctic environments were included into the model chemical scheme along with empirical parameterisation of the prompt re-emission from snow. Evaluation against measurements has demonstrated that the improved model chemical scheme allows reproducing observed depletion events at a number of Arctic sites. However, significant uncertainties still remain in the model parameterisation. This year the chemical kinetics of mercury oxidation by reactive halogen has been revised including the mechanism of AMDEs in the polar regions. Meteorological and other ambient conditions accompanying AMDEs have been analysed to reveal principal parameters responsible for temporal dynamics of oxidation processes. More information about this study is available in the technical report [Shatalov *et al.*, 2011].

It is expected that one of the main processes leading to activation of halogen chemistry during AMDEs (and ODEs) is production of sea salt enriched aerosol. Formation of young sea ice over re-freezing open leads is accompanied by formation of specific ice crystals, known as frost flowers [Simpson *et al.*, 2007]. Being enriched with sea salt brine frost flowers can be suspended by wind and produce sea salt aerosol as a source of reactive halogens. It is known that ice begins to form in sea water at temperatures around -2°C. So one can hardly expect the activation of halogen chemistry at higher temperatures. Besides, it is well known that solar radiation is required for both halogen photochemistry and mercury oxidation reactions. In addition, wind blown aerosol production is a function of the wind stress. As it follows from contemporary dust suspension studies [e.g. Gomes *et al.*, 2003] the flux of wind blown aerosol is proportional to the third power of friction velocity (U^*). Thus, the optimal conditions used in the model to modulate temporal variation of halogen chemistry are the following – activation of reactive bromine occur at temperatures below -2°C, in the presence of solar radiation, and is proportional to the third power of friction velocity normalized by monthly mean values.

The revised model was applied for mercury simulations on a global scale and detailed evaluation against measurements. An annual model run for 2005 has been performed with a preceding three-year spin-up procedure. The obtained simulation results for concentration of mercury species and wet deposition fluxes were compared with observations available from the EMEP [EMEP, 2011] and NADP/MDN [NADP/MDN, 2010] monitoring networks as well as from literature data. In order to extend the measurement database we have performed a literature survey on recent observations of mercury levels in air and precipitation all over the globe. Results of the survey are given in Annex A of the report. A selection of measured air concentrations of three mercury forms (Hg^0 , RGM, and HgP) used for the current evaluation of the model performance is presented in Table 5. In addition to this, observations of wet deposition fluxes from the EMEP and NADP/MDN were utilized in the analysis along with measurements at some Asian sites [Fu et al., 2008a,b; Guo et al., 2008; Wan et al., 2009a,b].

Table 5. Mercury air concentrations from the literature survey

Name	Lon	Lat	Hg ⁰	HgP	RGM	Year	Reference
Europe and the Mediterranean							
Alomar (Norway)	16.02	69.28	1.62			2005	EMEP, 2011
Pallas (Finland)	24.12	67.97	1.53	1.64		2005	EMEP, 2011
Nuuk (Denmark)	-51.65	64.18	1.41			2005	EMEP, 2011
Stórhöfði (Iceland)	-20.25	63.45		2.60		2005	EMEP, 2011
Aspvreten (Sweden)	17.38	58.80		9.22	11.44	1998-1999	EMEP, 2011
Birkenes (Norway)	8.25	58.38	1.90			2005	EMEP, 2011
Rorvik (Sweden)	11.93	57.41		9.74	17.47	1998-1999	EMEP, 2011
Rao (Sweden)	11.92	57.40	1.68	11.36		2005	EMEP, 2011
Zingst (Germany)	12.73	54.43	1.56	34.77	33.86	2005	EMEP, 2011
Mace Head (Ireland)	-9.90	53.32	1.55	7.03	28.09	2005	EMEP, 2011
Neuglobsow (Germany)	13.03	53.15	1.63	49.21	24.95	2005	EMEP, 2011
Langenbrugge (Germany)	10.75	52.80	2.00			2005	EMEP, 2011
Yarner Wood (UK)	-3.72	50.60		1.14		2005	EMEP, 2011
Cabo de Creus (Spain)	3.32	42.32	1.67			2005	EMEP, 2011
Sicily (Italy)	15.17	36.67		30.00	36	1998-1999	Pirrone et al., 2003
Calabria (Italy)	16.00	39.42	1.90	8.00	62	1998-2000	Pirrone et al., 2003; 2004
Calabria (Italy)	16.00	39.42		2.93	2.63	2003-2004	Sprovieri et al., 2010
Palma de Mallorca (Spain)	2.69	39.68		47.00	58	1998-1999	Pirrone et al., 2003
Cabo de Crews (Spain)	3.32	42.32		9.85	1.21	2003-2004	Sprovieri et al., 2010
Meze (France)	3.58	43.42			62.98	2003-2004	Sprovieri et al., 2010
Piran (Slovenia)	13.55	45.55		11.83	5.85	2003-2004	Sprovieri et al., 2010
Anatalya (Turkey)	30.34	36.47		32.00	15	1998-1999	Pirrone et al., 2003
Neve Yam (Israel)	34.93	32.67		60.00	35	1998-1999	Pirrone et al., 2003
Neve Yam (Israel)	34.93	32.67		38.93	13.55	2003-2004	Sprovieri et al., 2010
North America							
Barrow, Alaska (USA)	-156.6	71.32		24.00	82	1999-2004	Brooks et al., 2008b
Cheeka Peak (USA)	-124.6	48.30	1.50			2001-2002	Weiss-Penzias et al., 2003
Bay St.Francois (Canada)	-72.93	46.10		6.44	3.63	2002	Poissant et al., 2004
St. Anicet (Canada)	-74.28	45.12	1.65	26.00	3.00	2003	Poissant et al., 2005
Potsdam, New York (USA)	-75.00	44.75	1.84		4.20	2000-2003	Han et al., 2004
Mt. Bachelor (USA)	-121.7	43.98	1.77	5.20	43.00	2004	Jaffe et al., 2005
Sterling, New York (USA)	-76.66	43.34			6.00	2002-2003	Han et al., 2006
Stockton, New York (USA)	-79.38	42.27	1.83		5.70	2000-2003	Han et al., 2004
Detroit (USA)	-83.06	42.18		20.80	17.70	2003	Liu et al., 2007
Gibb's Ranch (USA)	-115.2	41.55		14.00	5.33	2005	Lyman and Gustin, 2008

Table 5. ... (continued)

Lesperance Ranch (USA)	-117.5	41.50	1.70	8.50	12.00	2005	<i>Lyman and Gustin, 2008</i>
Reno, Nevada (USA)	-119.8	39.57	1.60	7.00	37.00	2005	<i>Stamenkovic et al., 2007</i>
Reno, Nevada (USA)	-119.7	39.51	1.70	5.00		2007	<i>Weiss-Penzias et al., 2009</i>
Desert Research Inst. (USA)	-119.8	39.57		10.00	24.78	2007	<i>Weiss-Penzias et al., 2009</i>
Cove Mountain (USA)	-83.61	35.70		9.73	13.60	2002	<i>Gabriel et al., 2005</i>
Look Rock (USA)	-83.90	35.60	1.65	7.00	5.00	2004	<i>Valente et al., 2007</i>
Tuscaloosa (USA)	-87.62	33.23		16.40	13.60	2003	<i>Gabriel et al., 2005</i>
Caballo (Mexico)	-107.3	33.06	1.59		6.8	2001-2002	<i>Caldwell et al., 2006</i>
Weeks Bay, Alabama (USA)	-87.85	30.35	1.62	2.70	4.00	2005-2006	<i>Engle et al., 2008</i>
Huejutla (Mexico)	-98.42	21.13	1.32			2002	<i>Rosa et al., 2004</i>
Puerto Angel (Mexico)	-96.47	16.78	1.46			2002	<i>Rosa et al., 2004</i>
East Asia							
Mt. Changbai (China)	128.47	42.40	3.58	77.00	65.00	2005-2006	<i>Wan et al., 2009</i>
Kang Hwa (Korea)	126.30	37.72	3.26			2001	<i>Kim et al., 2003</i>
An-Myun Island (Korea)	126.32	36.53	4.61			2004-2006	<i>Nguyen et al., 2007</i>
Waliguan (China)	100.90	36.30	1.70			2005	<i>Wang et al., 2007</i>
Pudong, Shanghai (China)	121.53	31.22	2.70			2009	<i>Friedli et al., 2010</i>
Mt. Gongga (China)	102.12	29.67	3.98	30.70	6.20	2005-2006	<i>Fu et al., 2008</i>
Hedo, Okinawa (Japan)	128.20	26.80	2.04	3.04	4.51	2004	<i>Jaffe et al., 2005</i>
Mt. Leigong (China)	108.20	26.39	2.80			2008-2009	<i>Fu et al., 2010</i>
Africa							
Cape Point (SAR)	18.48	-34.35	1.23			1995-1999	<i>Baker et al., 2002</i>
Arctic							
Alert (Canada)	-62.50	82.47	1.53	102.60	44.4	2005	<i>Cobbett et al., 2007</i>
Zeppelin (Norway)	11.88	78.90	1.58	68.00	86	2005	<i>EMEP; Aspmo et al., 2005</i>
Amderma (Russia)	61.62	69.72	1.52			2005	<i>UNEP/AMAP, 2008</i>
Antarctica							
Neumayer (Antarctica)	-8.25	-70.65	0.99			2000-2001	<i>Ebinghaus et al., 2002</i>
Terra Nova (Antarctica)	164.12	-74.68	0.90	12.00	116.20	1999-2001	<i>Sprovieri et al., 2002</i>
McMurdo/Ross (Antarctica)	166.64	-77.86		49.00	116	2003	<i>Brooks et al., 2008b</i>

Simulated spatial distributions of concentration of mercury species in the ambient air as well as mercury wet deposition flux is illustrated in Fig. 45. Appropriate measured values are also given as coloured circles in the same palette. As seen concentration of Hg^0 has a pronounced south-to-north gradient. Mercury concentrations in the Southern Hemisphere are below 1.2 ng/m^3 , whereas in the Northern Hemisphere they commonly exceed 1.5 ng/m^3 . This is also confirmed by the observations (Fig. 45a). Elevated concentrations are characteristics of the west and east coasts of North and Central Americas, Europe, Middle East, South and East Asia, where the most significant anthropogenic and/or natural sources are located.

Spatial distribution of RGM also reflects the pattern of anthropogenic emissions. High RGM concentrations (up to 100 pg/m^3) are also predicted for the Arctic and the coast of Antarctica owing to AMDEs in agreement with observations (Fig. 45b). Simulated spatial pattern of HgP concentration has higher levels also over low latitudes since it is assumed to be a product of in situ oxidation reactions with ozone and OH (Fig. 45c). The model somewhat overestimate lower HgP concentrations in Europe and North America, probably, due to uncertainty of the model chemical scheme. However, it should be mentioned that available HgP and RGM measurements commonly relate to short-term periods (see Annex A) and should be compared with simulated annual values with caution. Spatial distribution of wet deposition is more mosaic than that of air concentrations due to spatial variability of precipitation

(Fig. 45d). The model successfully reproduces wet deposition measurements available in Europe, North America, and East Asia.

Fig. 45. Spatial distribution of annual air concentration of Hg^0 (a), RGM (b), HgP (c) and total wet deposition flux (d) over the globe in 2005 simulated with GLEMOS. Circles present measurement data.

More detailed comparison of modelled and measured values is presented in Fig. 46. The figure shows average latitudinal distributions of the mercury species and wet deposition. All four distributions have a maximum in temperate latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere accompanied by the largest spatial variability. It is caused by location of majority of emissions sources. For the oxidized mercury forms (RGM and HgP) two other peaks are also typical at high latitudes of both Hemispheres resulted from in situ production during AMDEs. Measurement data are in satisfactory agreement with the simulation results for Hg^0 . Relatively even distribution of this species is explained by its long residence time in the atmosphere. There is significant scattering of measurement data for RGM and HgP . The model generally reproduces the observed values but in some cases deviations are significant. It is connected with uncertainties associated with mercury oxidation chemistry and gaps of knowledge on chemical composition of these forms. Annual measured wet deposition fluxes well agree with simulations for Europe and North America. However, other parts of the globe are poorly covered with observations.

Details of the model-to-measurements comparison are given in Fig. 47. As seen discrepancy between the simulated and observed concentrations of Hg^0 mostly does not exceed a factor 1.5 (Fig. 47a). There is some underestimation of high values measured in East Asia. Scattering of the comparison results for RGM and HgP is much higher. The model tends to overestimate very low concentrations of HgP . However, as it was mentioned above this sort of evaluation of annual mean simulated results against short-term available measurements should be used with caution. It rather characterizes general level of the model performance by an order of magnitude. Most results of the comparison for wet deposition are within a factor of 2. The scattering is somewhat larger for high deposition fluxes. There is also some tendency to general overestimation of the observed levels by the model in Europe and North America.

Fig. 46. Average latitudinal distribution of simulated annual air concentration of Hg^0 (a), RGM (b), HgP (c) and total wet deposition flux (d) in 2005. The 90% confidence interval of longitudinal variation is shadowed in grey. Circles and whiskers present average measurement values along with standard deviation.

Fig. 47. Scatter-plots of the model-to-observations comparison for Hg^0 (a), RGM (b), HgP (c) and total wet deposition flux (d). Red solid line depicts the 1:1 ratio; dashed lines show different deviation levels: red – by factor of 1.5, green – by factor of 2, blue – by factor of 3.

Figure 48 presents evaluation of the modelling results for mercury wet deposition flux against available data from the EMEP [EMEP, 2011] and NADP/MDN [NADP/MDN, 2010] monitoring networks. Comparison of monthly mean deposition fluxes shows that the model adequately reproduces seasonal variation of wet deposition in both Europe and North America. Elevated deposition fluxes are characteristics of the summer period owing to increased oxidation of Hg^0 by photo-oxidants and subsequent scavenging by precipitation. There is overestimation of the observed values by the model in the second half of the year in Europe and in the first half in North America. In general the model somewhat underpredicts spatial variation of the observed wet deposition fluxes between different sites.

Fig. 48. Comparison of measured and simulated monthly mean mercury wet deposition flux in Europe (a) and North America (b) in 2005. Measurement data used in the comparison were retrieved from the EMEP and NADP/MDN monitoring networks for Europe and North America, respectively. Dots depict average measured and modelled value, whereas whiskers show the standard deviation over all monitoring sites.

Thus, the evaluation of modelling results against measurements has demonstrated satisfactory performance of the GLEMOS modelling framework in mercury simulations. The model successfully reproduced both spatial and temporal variations of Hg^0 air concentration and wet deposition. However, uncertainties of simulated oxidized mercury forms (RGM and HgP) remain significant owing to both gaps in knowledge on oxidation chemistry and lack of speciated measurements. Therefore, the work on improvement of the mercury component of the framework will be continued involving model sensitivity runs and comparison with detailed observations from field campaigns.

3. FUTURE ACTIVITIES

The EMEP modelling Centres (MSC-E and MSC-W) will continue their work on further development and application of their modeling tools on a global scale. In accordance with the EMEP workplan for 2012/2013 [ECE/EB.AIR/GE.1/2011/10] the Centres work on a global scale will include the following:

MSC-W activities:

- Refinement of the washout parameterization of the Unified EMEP model;
- Improvement of the biogenic emission modules (NO_x, BVOC);
- Evaluation of the model against non-European sites;
- Improvement and testing of the nesting procedure for global to regional scale computations.

MSC-E activities:

- Further development and improvement of the modular architecture of GLEMOS including adaptation and testing of the nesting procedure for multi-scale simulations and improvement of the framework computational efficiency;
- Incorporation of data on aerosols and atmospheric reactants based on external datasets or simplified chemical modules for improving evaluation of HM and POP pollution levels;
- Comprehensive analysis of major physical and chemical processes governing mercury cycling in the atmosphere based on sensitivity study and evaluation against detailed measurements (in co-operation with EU GMOS project).

In addition, MSC-E and MSC-W will continue co-operation with the EMEP Task Force on Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (TF HTAP) to develop a fuller scientific understanding of the intercontinental transport of pollutants; its impacts on health, ecosystems, and climate. In particular, the Centres will participate in a new round of the multi-model experiments including assessment of regional boundary conditions, source attribution, and sensitivities to future abatement scenarios.

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ANNEX A

OVERVIEW OF MEASUREMENTS OF MERCURY AIR CONCENTRATIONS IN AIR

Table A.1.

Station	Location	Category	TGM/GEM (ng/m ³)	RGM (pg/m ³)	PHg (pg/m ³)	Date/ Period	References
Arctic & Antarctic							
Barrow (USA)	156.62 ^o W, 71.32 ^o N	Aircraft		(900)		Mar 00	<i>Lindberg et al., 2002</i>
				(900-950)		May 00	
		Remote		70±5 (MDE)	10±1 (MDE)	Mar 01 – Apr 01	<i>Landis et al., 2002</i> <i>Skov et al., 2006</i>
				24±22 (1.0–97)		Feb 99 - Apr 01	
				34.07		Mar 01 - Apr 01	
				39.93		Mar 02 - Apr 02	
				81.84		Mar 03 - Apr 03	
	46.24		2001-2003				
	0.94±0.54 (BDL-2.44)	82±68 (14–355)	24±25 (3–116)	1999-2004 (Apr – May)	<i>Brooks et al., 2008b</i>		
Station Nord (Denmark)	16.67 ^o W, 81.6 ^o N	Remote	2 (max)			2000	<i>Skov et al., 2004</i>
			1.9 (max)			2001	
			5.7 (max)			2002	
			(0.93-2.1)			Feb 02 – Mar 02	
Terra Nova Bay (Italy)	164.12 ^o E, 74.68 ^o S		0.9±0.3 (0.29-2.3)	116.2±77.8 (10.5-334.0)	12±6 (4–20.0)	Nov 00 - Dec 00	<i>Sprovieri et al., 2002</i>
Neumayer (Germany)	8.25 ^o W, 70.65 ^o S	Remote	1.146±0.075			Mar 00 - Jul 00	<i>Ebinghaus et al., 2002</i>
			0.968±0.278 (MDE)			Aug 00 - Nov 00	
			1.043±0.284			Jan 00 & Feb 00 - Dec00 & Feb 01	
			1.063±0.235			Jan 00 - Jan 01	
			0.99±0.27 (0.16-1.89)	5 >300 (max)	(15–120)	Dec 00 – Feb 01	
McMurdo/ Ross (Island)	166.64 ^o E, 77.86 ^o S		1.20±1.08 (BDL–11.16)	116±45 (29–275)	49±36 (5–182)	Oct 03 – Nov 03	<i>Brooks et al., 2008b</i>
South Pole	102 ^o W, 89.997 ^o S				166±147 (11–82)	Nov 00 - Jan 01	<i>Arimoto et al., 2004</i>
			0.539±0.189 (0.24–0.82)	344±151 (95–705)	224±119 (71–660)	Nov 03 - Dec 03	<i>Brooks et al., 2008a</i>
Ny-Alesund, Zeppelin (Norway)	11.925 ^o E, 78.912 ^o N	Remote		(<2–12)	(<1–47)	May 2000	<i>Berg et al., 2003</i> <i>Berg and Aspmo, 2003</i>
			1.47			2000	
			1.56			2001	
			1.59			2002	
			(<0.1–3)			Feb 00 - May 03	
				>200 (max)	350 (max)	Apr 03	
	>140 (max)		May 03				
Ny-Alesund (Norway)	11.88 ^o E, 78.9 ^o N		0.17 (MDL) (0–2.2)	86±44	68±33	Apr 03 - May 03	<i>Aspmo et al., 2005</i>
			(1.5–1.9)	2 (<DL)	(3–5) (<DL)	Apr 05	<i>Ferrari et al., 2008</i>
			(1.2–2.3)	(<DL–11)	(<DL–7)	Apr 05 – May 05	
Hudson Bay (Canada)	85 ^o W, 60 ^o N		1.93 (med) (MDE)	22 (med) (MDE)	183 (med) (MDE)	Apr 01 – May 01	<i>Poissant et al., 2002</i>

Station	Location	Category	TGM/GEM (ng/m ³)	RGM (pg/m ³)	PHg (pg/m ³)	Date/ Period	Ref.
Churchill (Canada)	94.12 ^o W, 58.72 ^o N			78.8±54.1	588±312	2 Apr 04	<i>Kirk et al., 2006</i>
					2350 (max)	14 Apr 04	
				250±158	952±622	16-24 Apr 04	
				44.9±25.8	263±72.6	27 Apr 04	
				1260 (max)		8 May 04	
				29.6±33.7	239±164	19 May 04	
			1.28			Mar 04 – Jun 04	
	1.94±0.16		Jun 04				
	1.81±0.20		Summer 2004				
Alert (Canada)	62.63 ^o W, 82.97 ^o N	Rural-Remote	1.55±0.39 (<0.05–3.04)			1997-1998	<i>Kellerhals et al., 2003</i> <i>Kim et al., 2005</i> <i>Cobbett et al., 2007</i>
			1.55±0.41			1995-2001	
			1.1±0.2 (0.2–1.4)	6.5±5.7 (0.6–20.5)	50.6±54.6 (3.7–275.2)	Jan 05 – Mar 05	
			0.8±0.3 (0.0–1.6)	10.6±10.9 (0.4–77.5)	260.3±151.0 (19.3–693.9)	Mar 05 – Apr 05	
			1.0±0.4 (0.0–3.1)	64.1±52.2 (0.2–343.5)	64.8±79.8 (0.3–465.3)	Apr 05 – Jun 05	
			1.0±0.4 (0.0–3.1)	44.4±49.8 (0.2–343.5)	102.6±124.9 (0.3–693.9)	2005	
USA							
Walker Branch Watershed (WBW), TN	84.28 ^o W, 35.96 ^o N	Rural	1.99±0.43	50±30		Aug 92 – Sep 92	<i>Lindberg and Stratton, 1998</i>
			2.35±0.72	68±34		Jun 93 - Aug 93	
			2.05±0.55	66±40		Jun 95 - Aug 95	
Earlham College (EC), Richmond, IN	84.89 ^o W, 39.83 ^o N	Urban	3.88±1.96	156±84		May 93 - Oct 93	
			4.32±1.94	97±57		Apr 94 - Aug 94	
			3.34±0.92	103±40		Apr 95 - Oct 95	
WBW & EC		Rural & Urban	3.46±1.7 (1.93-4.73)	92±60 (50-257)		1993-1995	
Baltimore, MD		Remote		23±26 (5.0-139)		Feb 99 - Apr 01	<i>Landis et al., 2002</i>
Everglades, FL				15±12 (3.0-54)			
Durham, NC				16±12 (4.0-51)			
Athens, GA		Urban	3.9-8.7 (med) (1.9–77.6)	8-9 (med) 0–485		Feb 00	<i>Landis et al., 2004</i>
Dexter, MI CASTNET	83.9 ^o W, 42.4 ^o N	Rural	1.51 (med) (1.09-4.39)	2.21 (med) (0.19-31.0)		Nov 99 - Mar 00	<i>Lynam and Keeler, 2005</i>
			1.49 (med) (1.20-1.94)	2.92 (med) (0.30-38.7)		May 00	
Detroit, MI		Rural	1.6-2.1 (mean)		12.0-30.5 (mean)	Apr 96 - Oct 96	<i>Gildemeister et al., 2005</i>
		Urban	2.3-2.8 (mean)		42-54 (mean)		
Detroit, MI	83.08 ^o W, 42.32 ^o N		1.82 (med) (1.17-39.53)	6.41 (med) (0.64-51.0)		Jul 00	<i>Lynam and Keeler, 2005</i>
			1.68 (med) (1.09-15.74)	9.71 (med) (0.2-155)	18.3 (med) (5.70-60.1)	Sep 00	
			1.99 (med) (1.39-13.97)	9.14 (med) (1.94-270)		Jul 01	
			3.13 (med) (2.35-20.76)	22 (med) (9.49-52.0)	22 (med) (8.43-46.8)	Jul 02	
Detroit, MI	83.06 ^o W, 42.18 ^o N		2.2±1.3 (0.5-44.2)	17.7±28.9 (1.8-904)	20.8±30.0 (1.8-611.2)	2003	<i>Liu et al., 2007</i>

Station	Location	Category	TGM/GEM (ng/m ³)	RGM (pg/m ³)	PHg (pg/m ³)	Date/ Period	Ref.	
Cheeka Peak Observatory, Washington	124.6° W, 48.3° N	Remote	1.54±0.16 (marine)	1.6 (marine)	0.5 (marine)	May 01,	<i>Weiss-Penzias et al., 2003</i>	
			1.46±0.12 (continental)	2.7 (continental)	1.5 (continental)	Mar-May 02		
			1.61±0.13 (marine)		2.9 (continental)	Jun 01 - Aug 01		
			1.50±0.13 (continental)					
			1.54±0.09 (marine)	2 (continental)		Sep 01 - Nov 01		
			1.49±0.09 (continental)				Dec 01- Feb 02	
			1.51±0.12 (marine)					
			1.47±0.12 (continental)					
New York, Manhattan		Urban	3.84±0.10			Jul 00 – Oct 00	<i>Carpi and Chen, 2002</i>	
New York, Queens			2.69±0.03			Jul 00		
New York, Brooklin			3.70±0.08			Aug 00		
New York, Potsdam	75° W, 44.75° N	Rural	1.84±1.24			2000-2003	<i>Han et al., 2004</i>	
New York, Stockton	79.38° W, 42.27° N		1.83±1.32	4.2±6.4		Jun 02 - Apr 03		
New York, Sterling	76.66° W, 43.34° N		2.59±1.05	5.7±9.2		2000-2003		
				6.0±11.6		Jun 02 - Apr 03		
Cove Mountain, TN	83.61° W, 35.7° N	Rural	3.20±0.66 (1.75-5.28)	13.6±7.43	9.73±6.90	Aug 02 – Sep 02	<i>Gabriel et al., 2005</i>	
Tuscaloosa, AL	87.62° W, 33.23° N	Urban	4.05±1.28 (2.00-11.8)	13.6±20.4	16.4±19.5	Jun 03 – Jul 03		
Chesapeake Bay		Semirural, coastal	1.8±0.18	7.9±12.3 (6±7(night)-13±15(day))		Oct 02 – Nov 02	<i>Laurier and Mason, 2007</i>	
			1.7±0.14 2.5 (max)	9.7 (6±5(night)-16±15(day))		Nov 03 - May 04		
Baltimore, Maryland		Urban	2.2±0.21	16.9 200 (max)		Jan 03 – Feb 03		
Look Rock, TN	83.9° W, 35.6° N	Rural	1.64 (1.59-1.78)	5	7	Spring, summer 2004	<i>Valente et al., 2007</i>	
Athens, OH	82.12° W, 39.3° N	Rural	1.62±0.24 (0.78-4.38)	12.45±24.53 (0-461.59)	5.29±6.04 (0-76.82)	Jul 04 – Jul 05	<i>Yatavelli et al., 2006</i>	
Weeks Bay, AL	87.85° W, 30.35° N	Coastal	1.47±0.20	9.6±15.4	2.8±2.8	Apr 05	<i>Engle et al., 2008</i>	
			1.55±0.26	6.1±10.1	0.5±1.0	May 05		
			1.59±0.22	2.9±3.8	2.7±2.5	Jun 05		
			1.53±0.16	1.9±3.2	1.9±1.9	Jul 05		
			1.60±0.32	2.7±5.6	1.9±1.8	Aug 05		
			1.56±0.25	4.4±8.8	1.9±2.2	2005		
			1.80±0.21	4.5±5.7	3.4±4.9	Jan 06		
			1.75±0.25	3.8±6.5	3.6±3.7	Feb 06		
			1.76±0.18	5.0±6.9	4.9±5.4	Mar 06		
			1.67±0.17	2.9±6.7	2.7±2.6	Apr 06		
			1.46±0.18	1.5±2.5	2.2±2.5	May 06		
			1.68±0.23	3.5±6.2	3.4±4.1	2006		
			1.62±0.25	4.0±7.5	2.7±3.4	2005-2006		
Salmon Falls Creek Reservoir, ID		Remote	1.91±0.9	8.1±5.6		Jul 05 – Aug 05	<i>Abbott et al., 2008</i>	
			1.53±0.5	2.3±3.1		Nov 05		
			1.39±0.7	8.2±11.5		May 06 – Jun 06		
			1.32±0.3	3.2±2.9		Feb 06		
			1.57±0.6	6.8±12		2005-2006		
			1.19±0.8	14.8±14.5		Jun 06 – Jul 06		
1.68±0.6			Sep 06 – Oct 06					
Grasmere, ID			1.12±0.9	12.1±12.5	1.0±1.4	Jun 06 – Jul 06		

Station	Location	Category	TGM/GEM (ng/m ³)	RGM (pg/m ³)	PHg (pg/m ³)	Date/ Period	Ref.	
Mt. Bachelor	121.69°W, 43.98°N	Remote	1.77 (1.47-2.51)			Spring 2004	<i>Jaffe et al., 2005</i>	
			(1.4-1.8)			Mar 04 – Sep 05	<i>Weiss-Penzias et al., 2007</i>	
			1.54±0.176 (0.82-2.08)	43±82 (<MDL-600)	5.2±4.4 (<MDL-40)	Apr 05 – Aug 05	<i>Stawenzdruber et al., 2006</i>	
Desert, Research Institute, Reno, NV	119.8°W, 39.57°N	Urban	2.3 (0.9-8.6)			Feb 02 – Aug 05	<i>Stamenkovic et al., 2007</i>	
			1.6±0.5	37±28	7±9	Jun 05 – Aug 05	<i>Lyman et al., 2007</i>	
			1.8±0.3	9±8	4±3	May 05		
			1.3±0.3	43±25	10±21	Jun 05		
			1.6±1.6	64±27	4±3	Jul 05		
			1.7±0.5	51±43	7±8	Aug 05		
			2.0±0.4	34±27	6±3	Sep 05		
			1.4±0.3	6±7	4±3	Nov 05		
			2.3±0.4	1±1	5±2	Dec 05		
			1.8±0.5	2±5		Jan 06		
			1.6±0.3	13±6	12±4	Feb 06		
			1.7±0.5 (0.5-5.2)	19±24 (0-186)	6±8 (0-135)	Nov 04 - Nov 05		<i>Peterson et al., 2009</i>
			1.5±0.5 (0.5-5.4)	18±24 (0-187)	5±7 (0-144)	Nov 05 - Nov 06		
			1.7±0.6 (0.6-6.4)	41±45 (0-401)	13±11 (0-180)	Nov 06 - Nov 07		
				1.6±0.5 (0.5-6.4)	26±35 (0-401)	9±10 (0-180)		2004-2007
	1.2±0.3 (0.6-2.5)	87±57 (5.7-401)	10±10 (<MDL-180)	Jun 07 – Aug 07	<i>Weiss-Penzias et al., 2009</i>			
NV99, NV MDN	115.21°W, 41.55°N	Remote	2.2±0.6 4.4 (max)	2±3 15 (max)	27±15 65 (max)	Mar 05 – Apr 05	<i>Lyman and Gustin, 2008</i>	
			2.9±4.2 106 (max)	10±8 74 (max)	12±7 49 (max)	Jul 05 – Aug 05		
			2.0±0.8 5.3 (max)	4±4 14 (max)	3±4 19 (max)	Oct 05		
NV02, NV MDN	117.5°W, 41.5°N	Remote	1.7±0.3 3.7 (max)	5±4 25 (max)	16±8 39 (max)	Mar 05 – Apr 05		
			3.8±1.5 11.2 (max)	17±12 72 (max)	9±7 39 (max)	Jul 05 – Aug 05		
			2.5±1.6 16 (max)	24±30 150 (max)	5±3 16 (max)	Oct 05		
			2.8±2.1 10.7 (max)	2±7 42 (max)	4±6 23 (max)	Jan 06		
			1.8±1.4 (0.6-18.1)	26±26 (<MDL-143)	6±9 (<MDL-102)	Jun 07 – Aug 07	<i>Weiss-Penzias et al., 2009</i>	
NV98, NV MDN	119.72°W, 39.51°N		1.7±0.6 (0.9-4.6)	46±32 (<MDL-157)	5±4 (<MDL-55)			
Storm Peak Lab, CO		Remote	1.51±0.12 (1.6-2.15)			Oct 06 – May 07	<i>Fain et al., 2009</i>	
			1.6±0.3 (1.2-5.0)	20±21 137 (max)	9±6 33 (max)	Apr 08 – Jul 08		
China								
Beijing	116.7° E, 40.0° N	Suburban	(6.2-10.7)			Winter 1998	<i>Liu et al., 2002</i>	
		Urban	(8.3-24.7)			Winter, summer 1998		
		Suburban/ ind, rural	(3.1-5.3)			Winter 1998		
		Suburban/ ind, rural	(4.1-7.7)			Summer 1998		
Changchun	125.3° E, 43.8° N	Urban	18.4 (4.7-79.6)		145 (Non-heating seas) (22-398) 461 (Heating season) (148-1984)	Jul 99 - Jul 00	<i>Fang et al., 2001;</i> <i>Fang et al., 2004</i>	
		Suburban	11.7 (2.3-25.6)		84 (Non-heating seas) 211 (Heating season)			

Station	Location	Category	TGM/GEM (ng/m ³)	RGM (pg/m ³)	PHg (pg/m ³)	Date/ Period	Ref.	
Guiyang	106.7° E, 26.6° N	Urban	11±4	453.8±248.0		Dec 96	<i>Feng et al.</i> , 2002	
			13±9			Oct 99		
			8.56±5.50 (3.57-146.75)			Apr 00		<i>Feng et al.</i> , 2003
			7.45±4.15 (3.53-112.34)			Feb 01 – Mar 01		
			5.2±2.26 (1.70-70.0)			Jun 01 – Jul 01		
			8.33±4.64 (2.73-129.8)			Oct 01 – Nov 01		
			7.39			2000-2001		
			7.97±2.03 (1.90-405.63)			Spring 2001-2002		<i>Feng et al.</i> , 2004a
			7.16±3.89 (1.53-127.69)			Summer 2001-2002		
			7.86±4.31 (1.08-632.07)			Fall 2001-2002		
			9.54±5.16 (2.04-407.97)			Winter 2001-2002		
8.4±4.87 (1.6–550)	2001-2002							
Guiyang: - Matou	106.45-106.57° E, 26.58-26.70° N	Rural	7.5±2.5 (2.9-17.3)			Oct 01 – Nov 01	<i>Feng et al.</i> , 2004b	
			4.6±1.1 (2.9 - 9.0)			May 2002		
			4.4±2.3 (0.9-18.38)			Mar 02 – Apr 02		
			8.09±2.41 (4.62-21.55)			Apr 2003		
- Huaqiao			9.96±7.5 (4.2-37.6)			Apr 2003		
Guizhou, Lanmuchang	103.02-109.5° E, 24.5-29.22° N	Mining area	35.2±26.1			Dec 2002	<i>Wang et al.</i> , 2005	
			7.9-353.8			May 2003		
Beijing	116.5° E, 39.43° N	Suburban	111.2±91.8 (12.7–468)			1520±870	Winter 2003	<i>Wang et al.</i> , 2006
						750±200	Spring 2003	
						260±180	Summer 2003	
						400±150	Autumn 2003	
						1240±380	Winter 2004	
						170±12	Spring 2004	
						130±80	Summer 2004	
						430±50	Autumn 2004	
						680±620 (130-2400)	2003-2004	
		Urban				2210±1100	Winter 2003	
						1270±340	Spring 2003	
						810±240	Summer 2003	
						740±250	Autumn 2003	
						2130±420	Winter 2004	
						280±20	Spring 2004	
						180±120	Summer 2004	
						740±300	Autumn 2004	
	1180±820 (180 - 3510)	2003-2004						
Beijing	116.4° E, 39.9° N	Urban	8.3±3.6			Jan 05	<i>Wang et al.</i> , 2007	
			6.5±5.2			Apr 05		
			4.9±3.3			Jul 05		
			6.7±3.5			Oct 05		